

ROLE AND ROLE OF EMPLOYEES IN THE ENTERPRISE

Umirzaqova Shaxnoza Akmalovna

Student of the Kattakorgan branch of Samarkand State University

Sattarova Feruza Rustam qizi

Supervisor

Annotation: this article presents scientific considerations about the role of employees in the enterprise and their importance in production, methods and principles of employee management in the enterprise.

Key words: Enterprise, market economy, employees, production, organization

The current stage of development of the domestic and world economy is characterized by changes in the requirements for the personnel of the enterprise, an increase in the role of this component in the organization as a single system. In the context of the democratization of society and limited other resources, the well-known motto “Cadres decide everything!” regains relevance. And even if there are sufficient volumes of all the necessary resources, without an effective team, the most successful market strategy cannot be implemented, the continuity and rhythm of business processes are ensured.

In modern management, a person is the main subject of management. With this approach, not a person needs an enterprise, but an enterprise needs a person. A person's abilities are determined by his physical and cognitive capabilities. Along with these opportunities, working conditions and preparation for work also provide efficiency. Willingness to work is determined by a person's interest in work and satisfaction with it, motivation in accordance with the needs and results of work. When analyzing interest in work, special attention should be paid to the factors of interest - need, reasons (motives) for interest and motivation. Achieving the goal of the enterprise - ensuring high production efficiency depends on the diligent performance of their duties by the staff and the manifestation of initiative. For this, it is necessary that employees are really interested in their work.

Indeed, the assessment of the role of a person in the activities of the organization, in production has changed qualitatively. Today, human resource management is an important factor in ensuring the competitiveness of companies. Investing in the development of human resources is given even more importance than investing in the development of production itself. The value of human potential as a strategic factor in the success of companies has increased in the face of:

- ✓ globalization and internationalization of the economy;
- ✓ accelerating technological progress;
- ✓ development of information technologies;
- ✓ increased competition, etc.

Under such conditions, the success of any business organization will increasingly depend on its employees. Technological possibilities in many fields of activity have exhausted themselves, while the

human factor is not fully understood. Today it is not enough to understand the technical, economic and financial aspects of the organization, it is necessary to understand and learn how to manage the mechanism that determines the behavior of employees.[12:1]

The concept of "human resources" recognizes the need for investment in the formation and development of human resources, based on economic feasibility, with the aim of attracting a better professional employee, creating conditions for the creative and professional development of each employee, which entails the need for a more complete use of knowledge, skills of workers. Hence, the emphasis of work with personnel is also changing, in particular, efforts are made to develop and reveal the hidden capabilities of the employee. The problem is that people are the most conservative component of the organization, and the mandatory adaptation of human resources to new goals, methods and attitudes is required.

The most modern concepts of personnel management (strategic-oriented, system-oriented) are based on the principles of a systematic approach.

The use of a systematic approach is predetermined by a number of prerequisites, the presence of which is the basis for the possibility of its use. These most often include:

- integration of scientific knowledge, growth of interdisciplinary problems
- the complexity of the problems and the need to study them in the unity of technical, economic, social, psychological, managerial and other aspects;
- complication of solved problems and objects;
- increase in the number of links between objects;
- dynamism of changing situations;
- scarcity of resources;
- globalization of competition, cooperation, standardization, etc. [12:2]

Personnel management is a purposeful and joint activity of the organization's management. It includes company executives, as well as other specialists responsible for developing the concept of an effective personnel policy. Methodological bases of management of employees of the organization. In the process of personnel management, the development of a clear personnel management system, organization and subsequent planning of work with personnel, marketing policy in the field of personnel, as well as determining the potential of each employee and his needs in the organization.

References

1. Hamroyev, Halim Rajabovich. Tadbirkorlik asoslari: kasb ta'limi (iqtisodiyot) yo'nalishi talabalari uchun o'quv qo'l. H. R. Hamroyev; O'zbekiston Respublikasi oliy va o'rta maxsus ta'lim vazirligi. - T.: Yangi nashr, 2010. - 360 b.
2. R.S.Muratov, I.A.DJalalova, S.Sh.Oripov. Korxonalar iqtisodiyoti. Darslik. -T.: «Fan va texnologiya», 2014
3. Rasulov M. Bozor iqtisodiyoti asoslari. T., „O‘zbekiston“, 1999
4. Axmedov, A. (2022). *The negative effect of internet gambling on youth psychology. AsianJournalof Multidimensional Research, 11(5), 76-79*

5. Diyorugli, A. A. (2022). *The negative effect of public culture on youth consciousness and its social psychological features. Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities, 12(5), 289-291.*
6. Ugli, Akhmedov A. D., et al. "Depressive Behavior in Sports Competitions and Their Characteristics of Will-sustainability." *JournalNX, vol. 6, no. 04, 2020, pp. 50-53*
7. Axmedov A. ZAMONAVIY DUNYODA YOSHLARNI INTERNET TAHDIDLARIDAN HIMOYA QILISHNING IJTIMOY-PSIXOLOGIK MEKANIZMLARI (KIBERBULLING) //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. B8. – C. 1629-1633.
8. Axmedov A. OMMAVIY MADANIYATNING YOSHLAR ONGIGA SALBIY TA’SIRI VA UNING IJTIMOY PSIXOLOGIK XUSUSIYATLARI //Science and innovation. – 2022. – T. 1. – №. B7. – C. 1115-1118.
9. Saidov, A., & Saydullaev, J. (2022). УЗБЕК ОИЛАЛАРИДАГИ ТАРБИЯНИНГ ИЖТИМОЙ-ПСИХОЛОГИК АХАМИЯТИ. *Science and innovation, 7(B8), 1649-1654.*
10. Ismailovich, A. S. (2020). Problems Of Improving Psychology Of Healthy Lifestyle Of Uzbek Family. *Scientific reports of Bukhara State University, 4(1), 313-318.*
11. Sharifjon To'liqino'g A. et al. TA'LIM-TARBIYA TIZIMI VA O'QITUVCHILAR FAOLIYATIDA PSIXOLOGIK XIZMATNING AHAMIYATI //MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH. –2022. –T. 1. –No. 11. –C. 57-60.
12. https://studbooks.net/1528444/menedzhment/osobennosti_rol_personala_organizatsii